

COMPLEX MODEL OF THE PERFECT FLUID : QUANTUM UNIVERSE

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Abstract : We study the Schutz's variational formalism by introducing an exotic matter with an special equation of state in the form of perfect fluid Friedmann-Robertson-Walker quantum cosmological models in the presence of negative cosmological constant. We consider a $(4 + D)$ -dimensional Friedmann-Robertson-Walker type Universe having complex scale factor $R + iR_1$. We work in the cosmic string universe with a positive, negative and zero constant spatial curvature. In this approach the notion of time can be recovered and give rise to Wheeler-DeWitt equations for the scale factor R , corresponding to 4-dimensional universe and as well as R_1 for D dimensional space. We find the eigenvalues and eigenfunctions and then construct wave packets for each case. Finally, the time-dependent expectation value of the scale factors R and R_1 have been evaluated.

1. Introduction. The early twentieth century started with two revolutionary theories : relativity and quantum mechanics, which dramatically changed our view of the Universe. Quantum theory defines a wave function that describes all of the possible states of a quanta such as an electron. The wave function indicates the probabilities of the particle being found in the various states.

Cosmological models with a cosmological term Λ , describe the dynamics of our 4-dimensional universe. Now, if Λ is a dynamical variable (or vacuum parameter), then it is natural to suppose that in an expanding universe the cosmological term relaxes to the present tiny value by some relaxation mechanism which may be provided by a time-varying vacuum with a rolling scalar field.

Several attempts in these directions have been done, in the context of quantum cosmology, we suppose that Λ is dynamically evolving and it has the form: $\Lambda \propto R^{-m}$ where R is the scale factor of the 4-dimensional universe and m is a parameter. The Λ decaying models may serve as a potential candidates to solve this problem by decaying the large value of the cosmological constant Λ to its present observed value.

There are strong (astronomical) observational motivations for considering cosmological models in which Λ is dynamically decreasing as $\Lambda \propto R^{-m}$ with $0 \leq m \leq 2$. The case $m = 2$, corresponding to the cosmic-string matter has mostly been taken based on dimensional considerations.

In the quantum cosmology the Wheeler-DeWitt (WDW) equation which determines the wave function of the Universe can be constructed using ADM decomposition of the geometry in the Hamiltonian formalism of general relativity. However, quantum cosmology has many technical and conceptual problems. In fact, the WDW equation of quantum gravity is a

functional differential equation defined in the super-space which is the space of all possible three dimensional spatial matrices, and no general solution is known in this super-space. In quantum cosmology this problem is avoided by using symmetry requirements to freeze out an infinite number of degrees of freedom, leaving only a few for quantization process. This procedure defines a mini-super-space, where exact solutions can often be found.

The many-worlds interpretations of quantum mechanics is one of the most popular interpretation schemes for the wave function of the Universe. This interpretation differs noticeably from the Copenhagen interpretation of quantum mechanics since the conception of probability is abandoned in some sense. In fact, all possibilities are participated to create new universe with different possible eigenvalues obtained by measurements. The evolution of observables such as scale factor is found by evaluating the expectation values. In this case, like in the Copenhagen interpretation, the structure of Hilbert space and self-adjoint operators are still unchanged.

We consider matter as a perfect fluid. This description is basically semi-classical, but it introduces a variable, which can be identified as time and connected with the matter degrees of freedom, leading to a well-defined Hilbert space structure. Moreover, this allow us to treat the barotropic equation of state $p = \alpha\rho$, where $\alpha = \frac{m}{3} - 1$, the parameter m is restricted to the range $0 \leq m \leq 2$.

It is very convenient to construct a quantum perfect fluid model. Schutz's formalism gives dynamics to the fluid degrees of freedom in interaction with the gravitational field. Using a proper canonical transformations, at least one conjugate momentum operator associated with matter appears linearly in the action integral. Therefore, a Schrodinger-like equation can be obtained where the matter plays the role of time. Moreover recently, some applications of the Schutz's formalism have been discussed in the framework of the perfect fluid Stephani Universe and FRW Universe in the presence of Chaplygin gas.

Until now, quantum perfect fluid models with common equations of state have been constructed in the absence of cosmological constants. We can study the behaviour of the scale factor using the many-worlds and the de Broglie-Bohm interpretations of quantum mechanics.

Recently, the quantization of FRW radiation dominated Universe in the presence of a negative cosmological constant is discussed by Moneral et al, but their results are inaccurate and their relative errors range between 10^{-3} for the ground state $k = 1$ case, and 1 for the ground state of $k = -1$, which make their work unreliable. We generalize the previous investigations by studying quantum perfect fluid models for barotropic equation of state $p = \alpha\rho$, where $\alpha = \{1/3, 0, -1/3, -2/3\}$ correspond to radiation, dust, cosmic-string, and domain wall dominated Universe, respectively. Using complex or many world framework, the behaviour of the scale factors are determined. Moreover, the model, connected with an accelerated expansion for $-1/3 > \alpha > -1$.

It is important to mention that although recent observation point toward a positive cosmological constant, it is still possible that at the very early Universe the cosmological constant be negative. Moreover, we think it is important to understand more about such models which represent bound universes. This paper is organized as follows. We quantize the FRW perfect fluid models in the presence of a negative cosmological constant, using the

formalism of quantum cosmology. Here the quantum cosmological model with perfect fluid as the matter content is constructed in Schutz's formalism and WDW equation in mini-superspace is found to quantize the model. The wave-function depends on the scale factor R as well as R_1 and on the canonical variable associated to the fluid which plays the role of time T , in the Schutz's variational formalism.

We separate the wave-function in two parts, one depending solely on the scale factor and the other depending only on the time. The solution in the time sector of the WDW equation is trivial, leading to imaginary exponentials of the type e^{iEt} , where E is the system energy and $t = T$. We find the eigenvalues and eigenfunctions of corresponding WDW equations. We construct wave packets from the eigenfunctions for cosmic-string universe and compute the time-dependent expectation values of the scale factors for $k = 1, 0, -1$.

2. Cosmology of the perfect fluid model. We study the metric considered in which the space time is assumed to be of Friedmann-Robertson-Walker type,

$$ds^2 = -N^2(t)dt^2 + R^2(t)g_{lm}dx^l dx^m \quad (1)$$

Where $N(t)$ is the lapse function, $R(t)$ is the scale factor of the space time, g_{lm} is the metric on the constant curvature spatial section.

The metric (1) can be inserted in the Einstein Hilbert action with a perfect fluid in the formalism developed by Schutz.

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int_M d^4x \sqrt{-g} (R - 2\Lambda) + 2 \int_{\partial M} d^3x \sqrt{h} h_{ab} K^{ab} + \int_M d^4x \sqrt{-g} p. \quad (2)$$

Where K^{ab} is the extrinsic curvature, Λ is the cosmological constant, and h_{ab} is the induced metric over the three-dimensional spatial hyper-surface, which is the boundary ∂M of the 4-dimensional manifold M . We choose units such that the factor $8\pi G$ becomes equal to one. The last term of (2) represents the matter contribution to the total action, p being the pressure as such we assume the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ of space-time to be an exotic fluid, which obeys the barotropic equation of state

$$p = \left(\frac{m}{3} - 1 \right) \rho = \alpha \rho \quad (3)$$

Where p and ρ are the pressure and density of the perfect fluid, respectively and the parameter m is restricted to the range $0 \leq m \leq 2$. It is worth noting that the equation of state (3) with $0 \leq m \leq 2$ resembles a universe with negative pressure, violating the strong energy condition and this violation is required for universe to be accelerated.

From thermodynamical considerations and using the constraints for the fluid, if we drop the surface term in the action (2), and use the canonical transformation then the Super Hamiltonian simplifies to

$$H = -\frac{p_R^2}{12R} + \Lambda R^3 - 3kR + \frac{P_T}{R^{3\alpha}} \quad (4)$$

Where the momentum P_T , is the only remaining canonical variable associated with matter and appears linearly in the super-Hamiltonian. The parameter k defines the curvature of the spatial section, taking the values 0, 1, -1 for a flat, close or open universe, respectively.

We shall show an equivalence between ($k = 1$) and ($k = 0$) universes which are favored by observations. The continuity equation, by using the contracted Bianchi identity in (4+D)dimensions, namely

$$\nabla_M G^{MN} = \nabla_M T^{MN} = 0 \quad (5)$$

[Where 'D' is the extra-dimension]

$$\text{i.e. } \nabla_i T^{ij} = 0 \quad \therefore \dot{\rho}R + 3(p + \rho)\dot{R} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Using (3) into the continuity equation (6), the energy density in a closed ($k = 1$) FRW universe is

$$\rho(R) = \rho(R_0) \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)^m \quad (7)$$

Where R_0 is the value of the scale factor at an arbitrary reference time t_0 . Again, if we believe that the cosmological term plays an important role in vacuum energy density, then we may assume the cosmological term as

$$\Lambda = \rho(R) \quad (7a)$$

$$\text{i.e., } \Lambda(R) = \Lambda(R_0) \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)^m \quad (8)$$

Taking $m = 2$ and $\Lambda(R_0)R_0^2 = 3$ we have

$$\Lambda(R) = \frac{3}{R^2} \quad (9)$$

In the radiation dominated universe ($\alpha = 1/3$ i.e. $m = 4$) with a negative cosmological constants, the classical solution have been obtained by using Jacobi's elliptic sine functions.

In principle, it is very difficult to solve the WDW equation in the super-space due to large number of degrees of freedom. In practice, one has to freeze-out of all but a finite number of degrees of freedom of the gravitational and matter fields. This procedure is known as quantization in mini-super-space, and will be used in the following.

The mini-super-space can be obtained by imposing the standard quantization conditions on the canonical momentum and then, we may use the quantum mechanical replacements as $p_R \rightarrow -i \frac{\partial}{\partial R}$; $p_T \rightarrow -i \frac{\partial}{\partial T}$ as demanding that the Super-Hamiltonian operator annihilate the wave function ($\hbar = 1$)

$$\left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial R^2} + 12\Lambda R^4 - 36kR^2 - 12iR^{1-3\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right] \Psi(R, t) = 0 \quad (10)$$

where $t = T$ corresponds to the time co-ordinate. Equation (10) takes the form of a Schrödinger equation $i \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = \hat{H} \Psi$

Demanding that the Hamiltonian operator $\hat{H}$ to be self-adjoint, the inner product of any two wave functions Φ and Ψ must take from

$$(\phi, \Psi) = \int_0^\infty R^{1-3\alpha} \Phi^* \Psi dR \tag{11}$$

On the other hand, the wave functions should satisfy the following boundary conditions

$$\Psi(0, t) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial R} |\Psi(R, t)|_{R=0} = 0 \tag{12}$$

Using separation of variables

$$\Psi(R, t) = e^{iEt} \Psi(R)$$

the equations (10) takes the form

$$-\frac{\partial^2 \Psi(R)}{\partial R^2} + (36kR^2 - 12\Lambda R^4) \Psi(R) = 12ER^{1-3\alpha} \Psi(R) \tag{13}$$

Using equations (9) and (3) and putting $m = 2$, the equations (13) becomes

$$\frac{d^2 \Psi}{dR^2} - K'R^2 \Psi = 0 \tag{14}$$

[where $K' = 36k - 36 - 12E$]

Since the energy term grows faster than the potential for $\alpha < -1$ i.e. $m < 0$, this equation has a discrete spectra (E_n) with associated bound state eigenfunctions [$\Psi_n(x)$] only for $\alpha > -1$ i.e. $m > 0$.

3. Wheeler De-Witt Equation over complex space. Consider the metric in which the space-time is assumed to be of Robertson-Walker type having a complex scale factor $R + iR_1$, where the scale factor R stands for $(3 + 1)$ - dimensional space-time and $iR_1 (= a)$ is that for the internal space with dimension D . Avoiding the imaginary term, the line element can be expressed in form

$$ds^2 = -N^2(t)dt^2 + R^2(t) \frac{dx^i dx^j}{(1 + kr_4^2)} + a^2(t) \frac{dy^a dy^b}{(1 + k''\rho^2)} \tag{15}$$

Where $N(t)$ is the large function, $r^2 = x^i x^i (i = 1, 2, 3)$, $\rho^2 = y^a y^a (a = 1, 2, \dots, D)$ and $k, k'' = 0, \pm 1$, for flat, closed or open type of 4-dimensional universe and D -dimensional space. For simplicity, we assume the internal space to be flat i.e. $k'' = 0$

The form of energy-momentum tensor is chosen as

$$T_{AB} = (-\rho, p, p, p, p_D, p_D, \dots, p_D) \tag{16}$$

Now, we examine the case for which the pressure along all the extra-dimensions vanishes, namely, $p_D = 0$. In doing so, we are motivated by the brane world scenarios where the matter

is to be confined to the 4-dimensional universe, i.e. auxiliary hyper-space, so that all components of T_{AB} is set to zero but the space-time components and it means no matter escapes through the extra dimensions.

The scalar curvature corresponding to the metric (15) has the expression

$$R = \frac{-6RR_I\dot{N}\ddot{R} + 6RR_I\dot{N}\dot{R} - 2R^2\ddot{R}_1\dot{N} + 2R^2\dot{N}R_I - 2R_I\dot{N}^3K + R_I N^3 K^2 r^2 - 6R_I N R^2 - 6R\dot{R}\dot{R}_I N}{R^2 N^3 R_I} \quad (17)$$

Now substituting it into the dimensionally extended Einstein-Hilbert action (without higher dimensional cosmological term) including a matter term indicating the above mentioned exotic fluid the effective Lagrangian becomes

$$L = i^D \left[\frac{1}{2N} R R_I^D \dot{R}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12N} R^3 R_I^{D-2} \dot{R}_I^2 + \frac{D}{2N} R^2 R_{R_I}^{D-1} \dot{R} \dot{R}_I - \frac{1}{2} k N R R_1^D + \frac{1}{6} N \rho R^3 R_I^d \right] \quad (18)$$

where dot represents the derivative with respect to t .

Here we consider the lapse function,

$$N(t) = R^3(t) R_1^D(t) i^D \quad (19)$$

Thus, using equations (7a), (8), (9) & (19), we get the Lagrangian (18) as

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\dot{R}^2}{R^2} + \frac{D(D-1)}{12} \frac{\dot{R}_1^2}{R_1^2} + \frac{D}{2} \frac{\dot{R} \dot{R}_1}{R R_1} \quad (20)$$

We now defined the new variables

$$X = \log R; \quad Y = \log R_1$$

so that the Lagrangian (32) becomes

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \dot{X}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12} \dot{Y}^2 + \frac{D}{2} \dot{X} \dot{Y} \quad (21)$$

and by imposing zero energy condition named $H = 0$, the Hamiltonian constraint is then obtained through the legender transformation of the Lagrangian (21).

$$H = \frac{1}{2} \dot{X}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12} \dot{Y}^2 + \frac{D}{2} \dot{X} \dot{Y} = 0 \quad (22)$$

Here the mini-super-space in our model is two dimensional with gravitational variables X and Y .

To obtain the Wheeler-DeWitt equation, in the mini-super-space, we start with the Lagrangian (21). The conjugate momenta corresponding to X and Y are obtained

$$P_X = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{X}} = X + \frac{D}{2} \dot{Y} \quad (23)$$

$$P_Y = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{Y}} = \frac{D}{2} X + \frac{D(D-1)}{6} \dot{Y} \quad (24)$$

From which we obtain

$$\dot{X} = \frac{6}{D+2} \left[P_X \left(\frac{1-D}{3} \right) + P_Y \right] \quad (25)$$

$$\dot{Y} = \frac{6}{D(D-1)} \left[P_Y \frac{2(1-D)}{(D+2)} - P_X \frac{D(1-D)}{D+2} \right] \quad (26)$$

Substituting equations (25) & (26) into the Hamiltonian constraint (22) we obtain using the legender transformation of Lagrangian (21)

$$H = (1-D)P_X^2 - \frac{6}{D}P_Y^2 + 6P_X P_Y = 0 \quad (27)$$

Now, we may use the following quantum mechanical replacements

$$P_X \rightarrow -i \frac{\partial}{\partial X}, \quad P_Y \rightarrow -i \frac{\partial}{\partial Y}$$

by which the Wheeler-DeWitt equation is obtained

$$\left[(D-1) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial X^2} + \frac{6}{D} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Y^2} - 6 \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \right] \psi(X, Y) = 0 \quad (28)$$

Where $\psi(X, Y)$ is the wave function of the universe in the (X, Y) mini-super-space. We have, from (40)

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial X} - \left\{ \frac{3}{D-1} \sqrt{\frac{3(D+2)}{D}} \right\} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \right] \left[(D-1) \frac{\partial}{\partial X} - \left\{ 3 + \sqrt{\frac{3(D+2)}{D}} \right\} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \right] \psi(X, Y) = 0 \quad (29)$$

Using separation of variables

$$\Psi(X, Y) = \Phi(x), \Psi(Y) \quad (30)$$

We obtain the following equations

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial X} = \frac{\gamma}{D-1} \phi(X) \quad (31)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial Y} = \frac{\gamma}{3 + \sqrt{\frac{3(D+2)}{D}}} \psi(Y) \quad (32)$$

Where γ is assumed to be positive ($\gamma > 0$)

The solutions of equations (43) and (44), are

$$\phi(X) = c^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1}} \quad (33)$$

and

$$\psi(Y) = e^{\pm \frac{\gamma \sqrt{DY}}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (34)$$

Hence the solution of the WDW equation (28) are

$$\psi_D^{\pm}(X, Y) = A^{\pm} e^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1} \pm \frac{\gamma \sqrt{DY}}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (35)$$

$$\psi_D^{\pm}(X, Y) = B^{\pm} e^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1} \mp \frac{\gamma \sqrt{DY}}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (36)$$

where A', B' are the normalization constant, Thus we may write,

$$\Psi_D^{\pm}(R, R_1) = A^{\pm} R^{\pm \frac{\gamma}{D-1}} R_1^{\pm \frac{\gamma \sqrt{D}}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (37)$$

$$\text{or, } \psi_D^{\pm}(R, R_1) = B^{\pm} R^{\pm \frac{\gamma}{D-1}} R_1^{\mp \frac{\gamma \sqrt{D}}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (38)$$

Concluding Remarks. Using Schutz's formalism for perfect fluids we obtain a Schrödinger like Wheeler-DeWitt equations in which the only remaining matter degree of freedom plays the role of time. We also studied a $(4 + D)$ -dimensional classical Kaluza-Klein cosmology with a Robertson-Walker type metric having two scale factors R , for 4-dimensional universe and R_I for the D -dimensional space. By introducing a typical exotic matter with the equation of state $p = (\frac{m}{3} - 1) \rho$ in 4-dimensions, a decaying cosmological term is obtained effectively as $\Lambda \propto R^{-m}$. By taking $m = 2$, we find WDW in the complex space with scale factor $R + iR_I$. we have constructed wave packets by the appropriate linear combination of the eigenfunctions. The time evolution of the expectation value of the scale factors has been determined in the spirit of the many-worlds interpretation of quantum cosmology. The scale factors considered here never tend to the singular point, i.e. these models may not have singularities at the quantum level.

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